

Fabrication and improved optical properties of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites

Dalal Hassan, Musaab Khudhur Mohammed and Ahmed Hashim *

Department of Physics, College of Education for Pure Sciences, University of Babylon, Babylon, Iraq.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(01), 1186–1193

Publication history: Received on 12 December 2022; revised on 24 January 2023; accepted on 26 January 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0146>

Abstract

In this study, casting technique were used to fabricate of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanostructures with variant content of Fe₂O₃ NPs to employ in different optical fields. The results showed that the absorbance of PEG increases as the concentrations of Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles increase while the transmittance and energy gap of PEG decrease with increase concentrations of Fe₂O₃ NPs. The optical factors of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites are enhanced with adding of the Fe₂O₃ NPs content. The optical characteristics results of the PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites proved that may be employed in optoelectronic detector.

Keywords: PEG; Optical properties; Fe₂O₃; Nanocomposites

1. Introduction

Composite materials based on a polymeric matrix with embedded metal nanoparticles have attracted attention for use in the development of biomedical devices, solar cells, sensors, and capacitors, among other things, due to their distinct electrical, mechanical, optical, and chemical properties. It is possible to create a hybrid material with exceptional mechanical, optoelectronic, and dielectric capabilities as a thin film on a range of substrates by combining organic and inorganic components. As a result, there has been a lot of interest in the field of materials research in developing composite material based on polymers and nanoparticles that have high permittivity, low cost, and easily programmable properties [1]. Due to their covalent bond topologies, polymer materials often have undesired low dielectric permittivity and poor heat tolerance but desirable high breakdown strength and facile processability. In contrast to polymer materials, high-k ceramic materials have a desirable high permittivity and great thermal resistance, but due to their ionic link architectures, they also have an unfavorable low breakdown strength and a high level of mechanical brittleness [2]. Recently, the phrase "nanotechnology" has appeared, and it has drawn the attention of numerous researchers. As a result, various medical and technical sciences, among others, have advanced significantly [3]. The word "nanocomposites" refers to the end result of mixing nanoparticles with other common materials to create novel substances with unique physical characteristics [4]. The matrices materials that can show the interactions between the matrix and the second phase as well as nanoscale dimensions, dispersion, size, and form [5], is a key factor in determining the properties of nanocomposites. The concept of combining two or more different components into a single material offers virtually endless possibilities to create innovative engineering substances distinguished by a variety of different features. Composite materials are successfully used in practically all fields of study and commerce because of their vast variety of features. The automotive, electronics and electrical, aerospace and machine building, sport and leisure, civil engineering, etc. industries were particularly fond of composite materials [6–10]. PEG has a variety of useful properties, including great water solubility, minimal immunogenicity, and low toxicity [11]. It also has excellent protein adsorption resistance. Due to its unique magnetic, optical, and catalytic properties, iron oxide (III) (Fe₂O₃) is a material that has received extensive research. Excellent transport characteristics may be shown in the iron oxide nanoparticle. Numerous topics have attracted a lot of scientific attention, including catalysis, eco-friendly,

*Corresponding author: Ahmed Hashim

magnetic storage media, clinical diagnosis, and cancer treatment [12,13]. This work deals with fabrication and improved optical properties of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites to use in various optical applications.

2. Material and methods

Nanocomposites from poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) doped with Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles (size: 20- 30 nm, purity: 99.99%) were prepared by solution casting method. The PEG polymer solution prepared by dissolving of 1 gm in distilled water (50 ml). The Fe₂O₃ NPs were added to the polymer solution (PEG) with various contents 2.5%, 5%, and 7.5%. The optical characteristics of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites were tested using spectrophotometer (UV-1800⁰A-Shimadzu).

The coefficient of absorption (α) is calculated by [14]:

$$\alpha = 2.303 \left(\frac{A}{d} \right) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

which: A is the absorbance and d is the thickness. The gap of energy is given by [15]:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/m} = C(h\nu - E_g) \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

which C is constant, $h\nu$ is the photon energy, E_g is the gap of energy, $m = 2$ and 3 to indirect transition of allowed and forbidden.

The index of refractive (n) is defined by[16]:

$$n = \frac{1+\sqrt{R}}{1-\sqrt{R}} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

which R is the reflection. The coefficient of extinction (k) is determined by [17]:

$$k = \frac{\alpha\lambda}{4\pi} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

which λ is the wavelength. The dielectric constant parts: real (ϵ_1), and imaginary (ϵ_2) are given by [18]:

$$\epsilon_1 = n^2 - k^2 \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$\epsilon_2 = 2nk \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

The conductivity of optical (σ_{op}) is defined by[19].

$$\sigma_{op} = \frac{\alpha nc}{4\pi} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

3. Results and discussion

Fig.(1) demonstrate the optical absorbance of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites. The rise in absorbance when the rise of content of Fe₂O₃ NPs. This behavior due to the rise in charges carriers which absorb the photon [20-22] and therefore the transmittance reduces as shown in fig. (2).

The "coefficient of absorption" (α) expresses on the transition nature. Fig.(3) obtain the values of α for the PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites. it is clear from this figure that the $\alpha < 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which mean that the happen transition of indirect. Fig. (4,5) demonstrate that the gap of energy for "allowed and forbidden" for the PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposite individually. It is obtained that the E_g reduce when the increase of content of Fe₂O₃ NPs which due to creation of stages within band gap hence the value of E_g will be reduce [23,24].

Figure 1 Absorbance pattern of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites

Figure 2 Transmittance pattern of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites

Figure 3 The coefficient of absorbance pattern of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposite

Figure 4 Allowed energy band gap value of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposite

Figure 5 Forbidden energy band gap value of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposite

The "coefficient extinction" (k) and "index of refractive" (n) of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites are represent in figs. (6, 7). it is clear that the value of n and K rise when the rising content in Fe₂O₃NPs which due to rise of α and films density [25,26].

Figure 6 The extinction coefficient values of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites

Figure 7 The refractive index values of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites

The "dielectric constant" include "real and imaginary" of the PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposite are presentation in fig.(8,9). It is show that the ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 improve when increase of the content of Fe₂O₃ NPs which attributed torise of the value of n and k[27].

Figure 8 Real dielectric constant values of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites

Figure 9 Imaginary dielectric constant of PEG/Fe₂O₃nanocomposites

The "conductivity of optical" of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposite is established in fig.(10). The σ_{op} of PEG rises with rise of Fe₂O₃NPs content which due to related to the density and α [28].

Figure 10 Optical conductivity values of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites

4. Conclusion

This research includes the creation of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites and examination of their optical properties for use in optoelectronic detectors. The obtained results demonstrated that as Fe₂O₃ NP content increases, absorption of PEG raised and transmission decreased. With a rise of Fe₂O₃ NPs, the gap of energy reduced. The optical factors of PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites are enhanced with adding of the Fe₂O₃ NPs content. The PEG/Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites' optical properties studies demonstrated that these nanocomposites may be used in optoelectronic detectors.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Acknowledgment to University of Babylon.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest

References

- [1] Jebur, Q., Hashim, A., & Habeeb, M.A. (2020). Fabrication, Structural and Optical properties for (Polyvinyl Alcohol–Polyethylene Oxide–Iron Oxide) Nanocomposites. *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry*, 63(2), 611-623, doi:10.21608/EJCHEM.2019.10197.1669.
- [2] Roberto Ambrosio, Amanda Carrillo, Maria de la Luz Mota, Karla de la Torre, Richard Torrealba, Mario Moreno, Hector Vazquez, Javier Flores and Israel Vivaldo, Polymeric nanocomposites membranes with high permittivity based on PVA - ZnO nanoparticles for potential applications in flexible electronics, *Polymers*, Vol. 10, 1370; doi:10.3390/polym10121370, (2018).
- [3] Liu, L., Qi, Z., & Zhu, X. (1999). Studies on nylon 6/clay nanocomposites by melt-intercalation process. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 71(7), 1133-1138.
- [4] H.N. Obaid, M.A. Habeeb, F.L. Rashid, and A. Hashim, Thermal energy storage by nanofluids, *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 8(5), 143-145 (2013).
- [5] Slman, H. A. H., & Hasan, Z. A. (2021, May). Study addition of Fe₂O₃ Nanoparticles on Optical Properties for (PMMA-PS) Mixture. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1879, No. 3, p. 032100). IOP Publishing.

- [6] French, R. H., Müllejans, H., & Jones, D. J. (1998). Optical properties of aluminum oxide: determined from vacuum ultraviolet and electron energy-loss spectroscopies. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 81(10), 2549-2557.
- [7] Ahmed Hashim and Qassim Hadi, Novel of (Niobium Carbide/Polymer Blend) Nanocomposites: Fabrication and Characterization for Pressure Sensor, *Sensor Letters*, Vol.15, doi:10.1166/sl.2017.3892 , (2017).
- [8] Majeed Ali Habbeb, Ahmed Hashim, Abdul-Raheem K. AbidAli, The dielectric properties for (PMMA-LiF) composites , *European Journal of Scientific Research*, Vol. 61, No.3, pp.367-371, (2011).
- [9] Hind Ahmed, Ahmed Hashim, Fabrication of PVA/NiO/SiC Nanocomposites and Studying their Dielectric Properties For Antibacterial Applications, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, Vol. 63, No. 3, DOI: 10.21608/EJCHEM.2019.11109.1712, (2020).
- [10] Kadhim K J, Agoool I R and Hashim A., Synthesis of (PVA-PEG-PVP-TiO₂) Nanocomposites for Antibacterial Application. *Materials Focus*, Vol.5, No.5, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1166/mat.2016.1371> , (2016).
- [11] Hayder Abduljalil, Ahmed Hashim, Alaa Jewad, The Effect of Addition Titanium Dioxide on Electrical Properties of Poly-Methyl Methacrylate, *European Journal of Scientific Research*, Vol.63, No.2, pp.231-235, (2011).
- [12] R.M. Ahmed, A.A. Ibrahim and E.A. El-Said, Enhancing the Optical Properties of Polyvinyl Alcohol by Blending It with Polyethylene Glycol, *ACTA PHYSICA POLONICA A*, Vol.137, No.2, (2020).
- [13] Thakur, P., Thakur, A., &Yadav, K. (2017). Optical Properties of (Fe₂O₃)_{1-x}/(Cr₂O₃)_x (Where x= 0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5) Nanocomposites. In *Recent Trends in Materials and Devices* (pp. 145-155). Springer, Cham.
- [14] M. Jothibas, C. Manoharan, S. Johnson Jeyakumar, P. Praveen, Study on structural and optical behaviors of In₂O₃nanocrystals as potential candidate for optoelectronic devices. *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron*, Vol.26, pp.9600–9606, (2015), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-015-3623-x>.
- [15] T. Abdel-Baset, M. Elzayat, and S.Mahrous, Characterization and Optical and Dielectric Properties of Polyvinyl Chloride/Silica Nanocomposites Films, *International Journal of Polymer Science*, Vol. 2016, Article ID 1707018, 13 pages, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/1707018>.
- [16] ShaliniAgarwal, Y. K. Saraswat and Vibhav K. Saraswat, Study of Optical Constants of ZnO Dispersed PC/PMMA Blend Nanocomposites, *Open Physics Journal*, Vol.3, pp.63-72, (2016), DOI: 10.2174/1874843001603010063.
- [17] N. Mahfoudh, K. Karoui and A. Ben Rhaïem, Optical studies and dielectric response of [DMA]2MCl₄ (M $\frac{1}{4}$ Zn and Co) and [DMA]2ZnBr₄, *RSC Adv.*, Vol.11, (2021), DOI: 10.1039/d1ra03652a.
- [18] A. Alsaad, A. R. Al Dairy, A. Ahmad, I. A. Qattan, S. Al Fawares and Q. Al-Bataineh, Synthesis and Characterization of Polymeric (PMMA-PVA) Hybrid Thin Films Doped with TiO₂ Nanoparticles Using Dip-Coating Technique, *Crystals*, Vol.11, (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst11020099>.
- [19] Ali F Al-Shawabkeh, Ziad M Elimat and Khaleel N Abushgair, Effect of non-annealed and annealed ZnO on the optical properties of PVC/ZnO nanocomposite films, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, (2021), DOI: 10.1177/08927057211038631.
- [20] M. A. Habeeb, A. Hashim, and A. Hadi, Fabrication of New Nanocomposites: CMC-PAA-PbO₂ Nanoparticles for Piezoelectric Sensors and Gamma Radiation Shielding Applications, *Sensor Letters*, Vol.15, No.9, (2017), doi:10.1166/sl.2017.3877.
- [21] Naheda Humood Al-Garah, Farhan Lafta Rashid, Aseel Hadi, and Ahmed Hashim, Synthesis and Characterization of Novel (Organic–Inorganic) Nanofluids for Antibacterial, Antifungal and Heat Transfer Applications, *Journal of Bionanoscience*, Vol. 12, doi:10.1166/jbns.2018.1538 , (2018).
- [22] Falah Ali Jasim, Farhan Lafta, Ahmed. Hashim, Majeed Ali, Angham. G. Hadi, Characterization of palm fronds-polystyrene composites, *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, Vol.8 , No.5, PP. 140-142, 2013.
- [23] Hazim, A., Abduljalil, H.M. & Hashim, A. Analysis of Structural and Electronic Properties of Novel (PMMA/Al₂O₃, PMMA/Al₂O₃-Ag, PMMA/ZrO₂, PMMA/ZrO₂-Ag, PMMA-Ag) Nanocomposites for Low Cost Electronics and Optics Applications. *Trans. Electr. Electron. Mater.* 21, 48–67 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42341-019-00148-0>.
- [24] A. Hashim, Fabrication and characteristics of flexible, lightweight, and low-cost pressure sensors based on PVA/SiO₂/SiC nanostructures, *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron* 32, 2796–2804 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-020-05032-9>.

- [25] Ahmed Hashim and Ali Jassim, Novel of (PVA-ST-PbO₂) Bio Nanocomposites: Preparation and Properties for Humidity Sensors and Radiation Shielding Applications, *Sensor Letters*, Vol. 15, No.12, doi:10.1166/sl.2018.3915, (2017).
- [26] Alaa J. Kadham, Dalal Hassan, Najlaa Mohammad, Ahmed Hashim, Fabrication of (Polymer Blend-magnesium Oxide) Nanoparticle and Studying their Optical Properties for Optoelectronic Applications, *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, Vol.7, No.1, (2018), DOI: 10.11591/eei.v7i1.839.
- [27] Khalid Al-Ammar, Ahmed Hashim, Maithem Husaien, Synthesis and Study of Optical Properties of (PMMA-CrCl₂) Composites, *Chemical and Materials Engineering*, Vol.1, No.3, 2013, DOI: 10.13189/cme.2013.010304.
- [28] Ahmed Hashim, Zinah S. Hamad, Lower Cost and Higher UV-Absorption of Polyvinyl Alcohol/ Silica Nanocomposites For Potential Applications, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, Vol. 63, No.2, DOI: 10.21608/EJCHEM.2019.7264.1593, (2020).